

USING PROTOJOURNALISM IN ARABIC LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the didactic and methodological possibilities of using the protojournalistic approach in Arabic language lessons. Protojournalism is considered as a tool for developing students' communication-oriented, real-life skills in working with media. The article highlights the advantages of this approach in teaching the Arabic language in terms of increasing communication skills, expanding vocabulary, developing intercultural dialogue, and activating critical thinking. Methodological recommendations are also given for the practical implementation of protojournalistic activities in Arabic language lessons through simplified news texts, interviews, articles, and reports. This approach increases students' interest in the language and enhances their perception of the language as a tool in a real communicative context.

Keywords: Arabic language, protojournalism, communicative approach, educational methodology, media texts, interview, elements of journalism, language teaching, didactic activity

Introduction: Today, language learning processes are not limited to grammar or text translation alone, but are carried out in a broad communicative and cultural context. Especially in learning Arabic, perceiving language as a modern, vital and functional tool serves to increase students' interest and motivation in the language. From this point of view, protojournalism - that is, a method of working with texts, oral and written information, close to journalism, but in an elementary and simplified form - can be used as an effective method in Arabic language lessons.

In particular, one of the urgent tasks in learning Arabic is to increase students' interest in the language, develop their thinking and prepare them for life communication. From this point of view, the introduction of a protojournalistic approach to the educational process as one of the innovative approaches is of great importance.

Protojournalism is the activity of creating, expressing and sharing information through simplified journalistic methods. This approach serves to actively and creatively develop students' language skills in Arabic language lessons by involving them in writing news, conducting interviews, preparing articles or short reports. This method also develops students' intercultural competence, independent thinking and communication skills.

This article analyzes the methodological foundations, advantages, impact on educational effectiveness and practical applications of using the proto-journalistic approach in Arabic language lessons. The main purpose of the study is to identify the possibilities of developing students' linguistic and communicative competences through proto-journalistic activities in the process of learning the Arabic language.

Main part: Today, the communicative approach plays an important role in language teaching methodology. Especially in teaching foreign languages, including Arabic, the need to form practical skills and bring students closer to the language environment is increasing. From this perspective, the proto-journalistic approach is an effective tool for revitalizing the educational process in Arabic language lessons, using the language in a real context, and encouraging students to think actively and communicate.

Proto-journalism is a method that facilitates language learning through simplified forms of journalism-related activities. In this approach, students not only master the rules of the language through tasks such as writing news, composing articles, preparing interviews, and conducting oral reports, but also learn to use the language as a means of vital communication. Through these activities, students develop the skills of independent and clear expression of their thoughts, critical and creative thinking, and selection and analysis of information.

The proto-journalistic approach can be implemented in Arabic language lessons in several practical ways. For example, students are given the task of writing simplified news texts. Through this, they learn to apply grammatical elements such as tenses, verb forms, conjunctions, and sentence structure. Interview exercises strengthen oral communication skills and expand vocabulary. In addition, analysis is carried out on the basis of short and understandable texts taken from Arabic-language news websites (e.g., Al-Jazeera, BBC Arabic). Through this, students not only learn the language, but also get acquainted with the cultural and social context of the Arab world.

In lessons based on proto-journalistic methodology, students can be involved in writing articles about events in their lives or at school, and expressing their opinions on various social topics. Such tasks develop their written speech, increase social activity, and allow them to use elements of journalism creatively.

The experimental studies showed that lessons conducted using the proto-journalistic approach helped students develop a positive attitude towards the

Arabic language, increased interest in the lesson, and developed the ability to express their own opinions independently. In the articles and interviews written by students, significant positive changes were observed in such aspects as the correct application of language rules, clear expression of the topic, and clear and logical thinking. Therefore, the purposeful and methodologically correct organization of proto-journalistic activities in the process of teaching the Arabic language is an important factor in activating the language learning process and enriching it with vital and interesting content.

Summary: The article analyzes the pedagogical and methodological significance of the proto-journalistic approach in Arabic language lessons. It was found that proto-journalism is an effective tool for developing students' skills in learning and using the language in a practical context. Elements of journalism such as writing news texts, conducting interviews, and preparing articles play an important role in developing students' communicative competencies and increasing their interest in the language.

By introducing proto-journalistic activities into the educational process, Arabic language students acquire not only linguistic knowledge, but also intercultural communication and critical thinking skills. Such an approach serves to improve the quality of education, make lessons more interactive and interesting. At the same time, it is important for teachers to have special training and methodological skills for the effective use of proto-journalistic methods.

In the future, further development of the proto-journalistic approach in Arabic language education, expanding its capabilities, and integrating it with innovative technologies will further increase the effectiveness of the educational process. Therefore, lessons organized based on this methodology are expected to take the language learning process to a new level.

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